

Programs for Women Empowerment among Social Groups in Inclusive Finance - A Study

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Abstract

The SHG movement has become a socio-economic movement only because of its unique features of inclusiveness in implementation of social schemes and designing development and industrial projects added with Government patronage. The women folk have gained a lot from these SHGs. The rural women in selective who were longing for economic liberalizations have successfully got it through SHGs the famous result bear of this strengthening of their social status.

Keywords: SHGs, Microfinance, Women Empowerment, and Social Status.

Introduction

The initiatives on SHGs were first mooted by Mohamed Yunus, a noble laureate greeting from Bangladesh. The SHGs were started in 1975. Financial inclusion and provision of easy access to credit have always been the thrust areas of interest of Government of India. The success of SHGs movement is well understood, and it has provided a pathway for broader problems of empowerment and extension among various societies and communities. Socially and economically transparent, both suffering from Rural women in India. Individually, poor rural women can overcome economic withholding by Co-operation. The community approach is a viable setup to disburse credit to rural women. The organization for credit supply to the poor through SHGs is fast appearing as a hopeful tool for promoting earnings generation and economic empowerment for women in rural areas. The reality to empower rural women lies in catalyzing opportunities for them to even higher income to improve their standard of living.

Statement of the Problem

Socioeconomic empowerment can be performed through different means such as the provision of employment, provision of training on life skills, encouraging self entrepreneurship, direct transfer of

economic incentives, preparation of social security through populist schemes by Government and business inclusion through SHGs and other microfinance. Among all these tools of socio-economic empowerment, micro-financing assume center stage in India, because of her typical socio-economic system. Inequalities in the distribution of income and wealth, different culture, heterogeneous social groups, deep-rooted social stigma, self-restrained move towards adaptation to changes hinder the women populace in their bit to come to limelight.

Government and non-government organization are attempting hard to remove these hindrances. Womenfolk tend to respond to the changes in a slow and steady pace. However, the world is changing fast. Women need to adopt changes quickly. Excessive protectionism-personal and socially exposed in Indian women community make the problem further exacerbated. Self-Realization is a panacea, but the question is when the women realize themselves about their socio-economic empowerment. The SHGs provide an excellent platform for this noble attempt. Here again, dominance by few women is told only to uphold the truth in the say “woman is enemy of a woman.” There is a requirement for relooking into the functioning of SHGs so that all woman present to their collective empowerment.

Scope of the Study

The study is conducted to estimate the working of SHGs on the empowerment of women in Tumakuru District.

Objectives of the Study

- To study the performance of self-help organizations in Tumakuru District
- To decide the effectiveness of SHGs in socio-economic empowerment of women
- To analyze the changes in the social conditions of the SHGs members

Research Methodology

This study used a representative and exploratory research design. Analysis of Secondary data connected with shared thoughts of researcher’s scholarly peers, social leaders and experts in financial services has given stable based for descriptive analysis, the perceptual study to explore the opinion of members of SHGs about socio-economic empowerment through SHG. One hundred nineteen respondents selected in simple random sampling. Pilot tested structured questionnaire was determined 192. One hundred twenty-six responses were received, of which 119 were used. The response percentage is 62.

Data Collection

Primary and secondary data were used in data collection. For collecting original data, a well-structured questionnaire is essential to factor. Closed-ended questions mean the issues that ask the respondent to select an answer from a list of options. They provide uniformity of response and are almost easy to analyze. Secondary data is collected from the published sources, annual reports, namely and monthly bulletin of NABARD and RBI.

Limitations of the Study

- Restriction of data availability has confined the study only to the human side of micro- financing system.
- The study relies on primary data, which could be biased, and this study sample size only 119 respondents.

SHGs Bank Linkage Program in India

The performance of banks in linking of Self Help Groups to banking system sealed for their higher during the year 2012 – 2013.

**Table 1 Progress under Microfinance – Savings of SHGs with Banks Agency-wise
Position as on 31st March 2013**

Sl. No.	Name of the Agency	Total Savings of SHGs with Banks as on 31 March 2013		Out of Total – Exclusive Women SHGs	
		No. of SHGs	Saving Amount (Rs. in Lakhs)	No. of SHGs	Saving Amount (Rs. in Lakhs)
1.	Commercial Banks	(Rs. in Lakhs)	553257.05	3367566	444160.47
2.	Regional Rural Banks	2038008	152710.20	1683036	128054.08
3.	Cooperative Banks	1202557	115758.22	887917	79272.43
	Total	7317551	821725.47	5938519	651486.98

Source: Status of Microfinance in India 2102 - 2013/NABARD Report

Table no.1 Majority of 40,76,986 numbers of SHGs account with the overall savings of Rs. 5,53,257.05 Lakh in Commercial Banks as on 31 March 2013. Out of Total – Exclusive Women, SHGs account of 3367566 with total savings of Rs. 444160.47 Lakh. Other two banks, namely RRBs and cooperative Banks, are also active with helping of socio-economic empowerment. In the above table, there is a total 73, 17,551 SHGs account in different banks with total savings of Rs. 821725.47 of this total exclusive women savings account of total 5938519 with total savings of Rs. 651486.98 in the above three banks during 2012 – 2013.

**Table 2 Progress under Microfinance - Bank Loans Disbursed to SHGs
Agency-wise Position During 2012-13**

Sl. No.	Name of the Agency	Loans disbursed to SHGs by Banks during the year		Out of Total – Exclusive Women SHGs	
		No. of SHGs	Saving Amount (Rs. in Lakhs)	No. of SHGs	Loan Outstanding (Rs. in Lakhs)
1.	Commercial Banks	735577	1338500.70	633234	1148398.30
2.	Regional Rural Banks	312010	562652.22	273835	519987.39
3.	Cooperative Banks	172234	157383.52	130333	117045.34
	Total	1219821	2058536.44	1037402	1785431.03

Source: Status of Microfinance in India 2102 - 2013/NABARD Report

Table no. 2 showing the majority of Commercial Bank Loans disbursed to SHGs Agency-wise position during 2012-13 with a 735577 no. of SHGs and loan outstanding of Rs. 1338500.70 Lakh. Out of Total – Exclusive Women SHGs loan outstanding of 1148398.30 Lakh.

**Table 3 Progress under Microfinance - Bank Loans Outstanding against SHGs
Agency-wise Position as on 31 March 2013**

Sl. No.	Name of the Agency	Total Outstanding Bank Loans against SHGs		Out of Total – Exclusive Women SHGs	
		No. of SHGs	Loan Outstanding (Rs. in Lakhs)	No. of SHGs	Loan Outstanding (Rs. in Lakhs)
1.	Commercial Banks	2643971	2663944.38	2247717	2224398.25
2.	Regional Rural Banks	1327367	1052122.91	1145086	908473.35
3.	Cooperative Banks	480096	221462.43	364438	151132.89
	Total	4451434	3937529.72	3757241	3284004.49

Source: Status of Microfinance in India 2102 - 2013/NABARD Report

Table no. 3 showing Progress under Microfinance - Bank Loans outstanding against SHGs Agency-wise position as on 31 March 2013 on this majority of commercial banks Total Outstanding Loans against SHGs of Rs. 2663944.38 Lakh and Out of Total -Exclusive Women SHGs loans of Rs. 2224398.25.

**Table 4 Progress under Microfinance - Non-Performing Assets of Banks against SHGs
Loans Outstanding Agency-wise Position as on 31 March 2013**

Sl. No.	Name of the Agency	Non-Performing Assets of Banks against SHGs Loans Outstanding		
		Bank Loans Outstanding against SHG	Amount of NPAs (Rs. in Lakhs)	Percentage of NPAs to Total loans Outstanding
1.	Commercial Banks	2663944.38	217598.68	8.17
2.	Regional Rural Banks	1052122.91	43088.27	4.10
3.	Cooperative Banks	221462.43	18006.00	8.13
	Total	3937529.72	278692.95	7.08

Source: Status of Microfinance in India 2102 - 2013/NABARD Report

Table no. 4 showing Progress under Microfinance - Non-Performing Assets of Banks against SHGs Loans Outstanding Agency-wise position as on 31 March 2013. Of this table clearly stated regional rural banks have NPA level is very less compare to the other two agencies. RRBs NPA level is 4.10 percent, commercial banks NPA level is 8.17 percent, and cooperative banks is 8.13 percent. Total 7.08 percent of NPA of banks against SHGs loan outstanding.

Table 5 Reasons for Borrowing Loan

Sl. No.	Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Consumption	20	16.81
2.	Agriculture	03	02.52
3.	Animal Husbandry	17	14.29
4.	Income Generating Activities	50	42.02
5.	Asset Building	04	03.36
6.	Others	25	21.00

Source: Primary Data- Survey

Table no. Five showing reasons for borrowing loan with particular reference to women empowerment. 42.02 percent of the respondents are more favorable to taking the credit for income generating exercises; 21.00 percent of the respondents favor for another purpose, namely: children education purpose, marriage purpose, and so on. 16.81 percent of respondents for using target and 14.29 percent of respondents are using animal husbandry purpose.

Table 6 Interest Rate for Micro Credit

Sl. No.	Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	High	05	04.20
2.	Reasonable	55	46.22
3.	Low	59	49.58

Source: Primary Data- Survey

Table no. 6 showing the interest of microcredit. Majority of the respondents intends 49.58 percent are agreed a flat rate for a microloan, 46.22 percent of respondents agree on the reasonable price of interest, and only 4.20 percent of respondents are allowed on the high standard of attention.

Table 7 Level of Income of the SHG Members

Sl. No.	Income Level (in Rs)	Before Joining SHGs		After Joining SHGs	
		No. of Respondents	%	No. of Respondents	%
1.	< 3,000	47	39.50	18	15.13
2.	3,001 – 5,000	23	19.33	31	26.05
3.	5,001 – 8,000	19	15.97	24	20.17
4.	8,001 – 10,000	16	13.44	26	21.85
5.	10,001 & above	14	11.76	20	16.80

Source: Primary Data- Survey

Table no.7 showing the level of income of SHG members of before and after joining of self-help groups, this is the table clearly stated the level of socio-economic empowerment of woman in Tumakuru District after the joining of SHGs. Majority of 39.50 percent of respondents are income level of monthly Rs. Less than 3000 but after the joining of SHGs, the income level is increased. 26.05 percent of respondent's income of three to five thousand and also the ten thousand above income respondents are also improved. In this after examine that there is a significantly increased income per month of the respondents after joining SHGs.

Table 8: Sources of Savings

Savings	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Post Office	03	02.50
RRBs	45	37.80
Co-Operative Banks	10	08.40
Commercial Banks	61	51.30

Source: Primary Data- Survey

Table no.8: showing causes of savings of respondents. Majority of 51.30 percent respondents are experts of savings in commercial banks, 8.40 percent of respondents are favored to cooperative banks, 37.80 percent of respondents prefer to savings in regional rural banks, and only 2.50 percent respondents prefer to savings in the post office.

Table 9: Savings per Month

Sl. No.	Savings Level (Rs)	Before Joining SHGs		After Joining SHGs	
		No. of Respondents	%	No. of Respondents	%
1.	< 200	15	12.61	23	19.33
2.	201 – 500	19	15.97	42	35.29
3.	501 – 1,000	10	08.40	30	25.21
4.	1,001 & above	-	-	24	20.17

Source: Primary Data- Survey

Table no.9: showing respondent's savings per month of before joining SHGs and after joining of SHGs. In these surely stated respondents are conscious of savings every month. Only a few respondents are the manner of savings in a different agency of before joining of SHGs, but after the joining of SHGs majority of respondents are savings pattern is developed.

Table 10 Elevation of Social Status on being a Member of SHG

SL No.	Particulars	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Strongly Agree	32	26.89
2.	Agree	49	41.18
3.	No Objection	30	25.21
4.	Disagree	08	06.72

Source: Primary Data- Survey

Table no.10: showing the respondent's social aspect details of after joining self-help groups. In this table stated 26.89 percent are hugely accepted, 41.18 percent of respondents agree, 25.21 percent of respondents are average, and only 6.72 percent of respondents disagree. The social aspect is an essential aspect of a woman.

Table 11 Suggestions to Improve the SHGs

Sl. No.	Suggestions	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	To improve the creditability	31	26.05
2.	Need for good planning	24	20.17
3.	To reduce interest	39	32.77
4.	To improve savings	15	12.60
5.	Coordination	10	08.40

Source: Primary Data- Survey

Table no.11: shows suggestions from the respondents to gain the SHGs. 32.77 percent respondents are suggested to reduce of interest, 26.05 percent of respondents are recommended to enhance the credit facility, 20.17 percent of respondents are advise the need for well planning, 12.60 percent respondents intimate to upgrade savings pattern, and 8.40 percent of respondents are supported coordination with SHGs members.

Major Findings of the Study

- All the respondents have developed the ability of with the activities of SHGs
- Study reveals that the majority of the members being to an agricultural family
- 42.02 percent of the respondents are more favorable to taking the loan for income generating activities

- Majority of the respondents means 49.58 percent are given on a low rate for microcredit
- Majority of 51.30 percent of respondents are sources of savings in commercial banks
- After joining the SHGs, the member's income has increased considerably
- The primary purpose of savings of the members for the children education and marriage purpose
- After joining SHGs with they have got self-confident and living with community
- Socioeconomic status of the respondents has improved in the form of family literacy, perception, and education on becoming members of SHGs

Suggestions

- Group activity needs to be organized in the interest of building up of strong SHGs. Selection of a leader needs to be maintained carefully.
- Should provide self-employment loan for specific SHGs members
- The training for the members is necessary to run the SHGs successfully. Skill development of women will empower them to take up enterprises and thereby provide more to their family income.
- The government should make budgetary allocation for preparation for the SHGs members.

Conclusion

Study on Socio-economic Empowerment of women through Micro financing – A Study of Women SHGs in Tumakuru District has brought out the most consigning issue of women empowerment through financial inclusion. This experimental study has clearly emphasized that SHGs have played a significant role in women empowerment in the rural area. Individual packets in the rural area need extra attention in as much as women empowerment is a concern. The social stigma yet married women shall not come to limelight on public platforms is still acting as a block in women empowerment. The SHGs, along with the political stipulations and increased education level of women, would undoubtedly emancipate them from the social, economic shackles.

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